

Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Library Research

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding *Internet Banking* in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library *research*. The data collection technique is: *first*, open the *Perish/Harzing* software, then search for journals based on the *title words category* with the key word " *Internet Banking* " within the entire year period. *Second*, collect journal title data in *Microsoft Excel*, and identify duplicate journal titles. *Third*, download files in RIS (*Research Information Systems*) and PDF (*Portable Document Format*) format from all journals for which data has been collected. *Fourth*, enter the RIS data *file* into *Mendeley software Desktop*. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around *Internet Banking* based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There were 271 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding previous research journals, researchers found 271 Research topics regarding *Internet Banking* in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around *Internet Banking*, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: *Internet Banking*; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

The increasingly modern era has become a demand for industry to create new innovations that are beneficial to consumers. One of these innovations is internet banking in banking. The use of internet banking can make it easier for customers to access information related to funds stored in the bank and is also a solution for developing bank infrastructure at a more cost efficient rate than providing ATM machines in various locations (Sri Maharsi and Fenny, 2006).

Internet banking can also benefit customers because they can access banking facilities via their smartphones. The banking industry is starting to develop in cyberspace with transactions being processed online using the more flexible internet. The ease of use of internet banking services also influences customer comfort in managing their accounts at any time with minimal costs. Apart from that, internet banking also offers convenience and better prices for customers (Barusman, 2010).

There are quite a lot of scientific publications about internet banking, according to a search on the Garuda *website* (Garba Rujukan Digital) there are 302 studies. The most research occurred in 2021 with 39 studies on internet banking. This shows that the development of internet *banking* is very rapid in the sharia banking industry.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding *Internet Banking* use library research (*library research*). The difference between this

research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding *Internet Banking*, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around *Internet Banking*, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Internet banking is the use of internet technology to carry out banking transactions connected via the internet network. This activity uses the internet as an intermediary between customers and the bank. Furthermore, transactions are virtual and there are no face-to-face activities between customers and the bank officers concerned (Directorate Study And Arrangement Banking Bank Indonesia).

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact *factor*. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as *Web of Science*, *Scopus*, or *Google Scholar*. Bibliometric methods can also be

used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. *VOSviewer* can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as *Scopus*, *Web of Science*, or *Google Scholar*. *VOSviewer* can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, *VOSviewer* can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of *VOSviewer* is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. *VOSviewer* can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a *mix-method approach*, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library *research*. The object of the research is *Internet Banking* in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about *Internet Banking* originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda *website* (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are *Microsoft Excel*, *Mendeley Desktop*, *VOSviewer*, and *Perish software*.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda *website* and *Perish software*, then search for journal titles based on the *title words* category with the keyword "*Internet Banking*" for the entire year (2002 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in *Microsoft Excel*, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (*Research Information Systems*) and PDF (*Portable Document Format*) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into *Mendeley Desktop software*.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on *Mendeley Desktop* based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the *VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software* based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research space based on library *research*. (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results on the Garuda *website* (Garba Rujukan Digital) regarding internet banking during the period 2002 to 2022 show a significant increase in

the last 5 years. From this search, publication data was obtained in the form of articles totaling 287 titles from accredited national journals.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Internet Banking by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2002	1	2012	13	2018	33
2005	1	2013	19	2019	30
2007	1	2014	19	2020	30
2008	1	2015	22	2021	37
2010	2	2016	28	2022	28
2011	7	2017	15		
Total 287					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft *Excel 2016*.

Table 2 shows that there are 35 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles on Internet Banking in Islamic and conventional financial institutions. The FEB Student Journal is the affiliate/journal publishing institution that publishes the largest number of research results on Internet Banking, with 17 articles.

Table 2. Affiliation/institution of journal publishers about Internet Banking

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
FEB Student Scientific Journal	17
Journal of Business Administration, Journal of Management and Entrepreneurship	5
CALYPTRA, Journal of Finance and Banking, Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Studies	4
Accounting E-Journal, Management E-Journal, EMBA Journal: Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research Journal, Management and Business Journal SEGMENT	3
Al-Amwal: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking, Assets: Journal of Accounting and Education, Economic Dynamics - Journal of Economics and Business, Diponegoro Journal of Accounting, Diponegoro Law Journal, Journal of Economics, Business, & Accountancy Ventura, Jurnal Akrab Juara, Multiparadigm Accounting Journal, Accounting Dynamics Journal, Ecodemica Journal: Journal of Management and Business Economics, Journal of Economics, Management and Banking, Infokam Scientific Journal, MAKSITEK SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL, Mirai Management Journal, Organization and Management Journal, Journal of Information Technology and Computer Science Development, Visionida Journal, KEUNIS, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, LEX ET SOCIETATIS, Nominal: Accounting and Management Research Barometer,	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft *Excel 2016*.

In table 3, it can be seen that the most productive research was carried out by Ronny from STIE Perbanas Surabaya, who wrote 6 articles.

Table 3. Researcher productivity around Internet Banking

Researcher	Number of Publications
Ronny (STIE Perbanas Surabaya)	6
Ellen Theresia Sihotang (STIE Perbanas Surabaya)	3
Ana Fitriana (STMIK Pontianak), Alvira Lia Alamanda Dewi (Brawijaya University), Faramita Dwitama (Gunadarma University)	2
(Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)	

Source: Processed data, Microsoft *Excel 2016*.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Research results based on searches on the Garuda *website* (Digital Referral Garba) were then exported in RIS (*Research Information Systems*) format, which was then input and analyzed using *VOSviewer*. The results are as follows:

rate, reliability, researcher, responsiveness, satisfaction, service quality, significant impact, validity.

- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 24 topics, namely: *age, application, banking industry, banking performance, commercial bank, company, credit risk, earnings, effect, financial performance, frequency, IDX, increase, Indonesian stock exchange, insignificant effect, internet financial reporting, liquidity, multiple linear regression, performance, positive effect, roa, significant effect, size, software.*
- Cluster 5. The color purple consists of 24 topics, namely: *bank bri, bank customer, computer self efficacy, credibility, customer intention, customer interest, data analysis technique, f test, function, information technology, internet banking adoption, internet banking use, Mandiri internet banking, multiple linear regression analysis, perceived ease, perceived risk, perceived usefulness, perception, risk, sample, service feature, significance value t test, value.*
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 16 topic items, namely: *Bank Negara Indonesia, Covid, cyber crime, determination, financial transactions, Ibank, internet, security, questionnaire, pandemic, payment, Persero, PT Bank Mandiri, TBK, technology, transactions.*
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 12 topics, namely: *bank service, banking service, customer dissatisfaction, determinant, e-CRM, internet banking service, internet network, lack, rest, service, social influence, technology.*
- Cluster 8. The brown color consists of 9 topics, namely: *atm, convenience, facility, mobile banking, positive influence, r square, respondents, usability, user satisfaction.*

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding *Internet Banking in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions*

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 271 Research topics regarding *Internet Banking* in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

- INTERNET BANKING IN Indonesia
- Analysis of Behavioral Intentions to Use Internet Banking among Internet Users in Surabaya
- Determinants of Adoption of Internet Banking Services: Perspective of Banking Consumers in Yogyakarta Special Region
- Analysis of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction: Case Study of Internet Banking Services (Klik BCA) at PT. BCA, Tbk. Merdeka Branch
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY ON CONSUMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN PRIVATE BANK
- THE INFLUENCE OF BENEFITS AND EASE OF USE ON POSITIVE ATTITUDE TO USING INTERNET BANKING (SURVEY ON CLICK BCA SEMARANG USERS)
- ANTECEDENTS AND CONSEQUENCES OF CUSTOMER ATTITUDES IN USING INTERNET BANKING USING THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) FRAMEWORK (SURVEY ON KlikBCA USERS)
- Factors that Influence the Use of Internet Banking Services by Bank Customers in Indonesia
- Attitude Factors that Influence Interest in Using Internet Banking

- CSF DETERMINATION ON INTERNET BANKING WEBSITES IS REVIEWED FROM THE ASPECT OF USER NEEDS AS INDIVIDUAL CUSTOMERS WITH CASE STUDY OF BCA, BANK MANDIRI, AND BNI
- ATTITUDE FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING
- FACTORS DETERMINING ACCEPTANCE LEVEL OF INTERNET BANKING IMPLEMENTATION
- MEASURING THE QUALITY OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES
- ADOPTION OF INTERNET BANKING FOR ADVANTAGE IN BANKING PERFORMANCE: A STUDY OF THE BANKING SECTOR IN INDONESIA
- The Influence of Trust, Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Convenience, and Perceived Comfort on Interest in Using the Internet Banking System
- INDIVIDUAL INTEREST TOWARDS USE OF INTERNET BANKING: A MODIFIED THEORY OF PLANNED BEHAVIOR APPROACH
- Behavioral Intention in Internet Banking Adoption: Theory Decomposed of TPB
- Non-Financial Performance Analysis of Internet Banking Viewed from the Customer's Perspective
- E-SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AND LOYALTY IN USE OF INTERNET BANKING
- The Influence of Attitudes, Norms and Control Subjective Interests Attitudes to Using Internet Banking In BRI Kotamobagu Branch
- Analysis of the Influence of Internet Banking Service Quality and Level of Satisfaction on Customer Loyalty at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Jamsostek Jakarta Sub Branch Office
- FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMERS' INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING USING AUTOMATED CASH TELLERS
- Security System PT BANK MANDIRI (Persero) Tbk Internet Banking Service.
- Integrated Marketing Communication To Enhance Active Users of Internet Banking Service: Case Study Bank XYZ
- Determinants of the Intention to Use Internet Banking
- Security of Internet Banking Services in Banking Transactions
- THE QUALITY OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES AND THEIR CHARACTERISTICS BASED ON FREQUENCY OF USE
- Comparative Performance Analysis of Banking For Implementing Internet Banking
- The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Convenience, Perceived Risk and Trust on Interest in Using Internet Banking
- Determinants of Attitude and Its Influence on Interest in Using Internet Banking
- ANALYSIS OF INDIVIDUAL BEHAVIOR IN ACCEPTING INTERNET BANKING BASED SYSTEMS
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING USE ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (Study at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Bontang Branch)
- The Influence of Attitude, Perceived Behavioral Control, Experience and Trust on Interest in Using Internet Banking Services

- The Influence of Perceived Web Security and Lifestyle Suitability on Interest in Using Internet Banking: Modified Technology Acceptance Model
- Brawijaya University Students' Interest in Using Internet Banking in Tuition Payment Transactions: Modified Technology Acceptance Model Approach
- The Influence of Confidence and Technology Trust on Interest in Using Internet Banking in Malang: Reduced Theory of Reason Action
- RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS CUSTOMERS USING INTERNET BANKING
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, PERCEIVED EASE OF USE, PERCEIVED RISK AND SERVICE FEATURES ON USING BCA INTERNET BANKING
- The Influence of Internet Banking on Banking Performance in Indonesia (Empirical Study of Banks Listed on the IDX)
- Analysis of the Effect of Servqual, Satisfaction and Trust on Customer Loyalty of Internet Banking Service Users Using the Structural Equation Modeling Method (Case Study: Bank "X")
- PERCEIVED USEFULNESS, PERCEIVED EASE OF USE, PERCEIVED RISK IMPACT TO LECTURERS' INTERNET BANKING ADOPTION
- THE INFLUENCE OF TRUST, PERCEPTION OF USEFULNESS, PERCEPTION OF EASE, AND PERCEPTION OF COMFORT ON INTEREST IN USING THE INTERNET BANKING SYSTEM IN CUSTOMERS OF BANK MUAMALAT BANTU BANTU MADIUN
- THE EFFECT OF USE OF INTERNET BANKING ON CUSTOMER'S SENSE OF SECURITY, TRUST AND LOYALTY IN INCREASING BANK BALANCE
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF EASE OF USE, TRUST, COMPUTER ANXIETY AND SERVICE QUALITY ON INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING
- THE INFLUENCE OF OVERALL INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (Case Study at Bank BNI Pekalongan)
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, EASE OF USE, TRANSACTION RISKS, AND SERVICE FEATURES ON CUSTOMER RETURN INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF BENEFITS, PERCEPTIONS OF EASY, SECURITY AND AVAILABILITY OF FEATURES ON BANK CUSTOMERS' RE-INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING (STUDY ON THE BRI INTERNET BANKING SERVICE PROGRAM)
- ANALYSIS OF TRUST FACTORS AND THE INFLUENCE OF TRUST ON INTERNET BANKING CUSTOMER LOYALTY
- Analysis of Factors that Influence Customer Interest in Using BNI New Internet Banking Services Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Framework (Empirical Study of BNI Customers at Manado Main Branch Office)
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY AND BRAND EQUITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION AT PT. MANDIRI SYARIAH BANK KCP MEDAN AKSARA
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING UTILIZATION FACTORS ON USER SATISFACTION (Study at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia Kawi Branch, Malang)
- Determinant Factors of Individual Interest in Using Internet Banking-Based Information Systems

- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF BENEFITS, EASE OF USE AND CREDIBILITY ON INTERNET BANKING REPEAT USE INTENTIONS WITH USAGE ATTITUDE AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE (Empirical Study: Internet Banking Service Customers in Indonesia)
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF CUSTOMER'S PERSONAL DATA IN INTERNET BANKING SERVICES
- THE APPLICATION OF TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL ON INTERNET BANKING USERS IN THE CITY OF DENPASAR
- TAM Application, Risk Perception, and Trust in Explaining People's Intentions to Use Internet Banking
- ANALYSIS OF ADOPTION OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES BY BANKING CUSTOMERS IN PEKANBARU (Technology Acceptance Model) Eni Noviarni
- The Influence of Risk, Benefits and Ease of Use on Customer Confidence in Using Internet Banking in Yogyakarta (Case Study of Bank Mandiri Customers)
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING INTERNET BANKING USE IN BANJARMASIN
- APPLICATION OF ACCEPTANCE MODEL TECHNOLOGY ON CUSTOMER INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING
- Factors that Influence Customer Interest in Using Internet Banking Using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) at Bank Mandiri
- The Influence of Trust, Perception of Usefulness, Perception of Ease of Use on Attitudes of Internet Banking Users (Study on Customers of PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia Kediri Branch Office)
- Factors that Influence Customers to Adopt Internet Banking
- The Influence of Perceived Benefits and Perceived Convenience on Attitudes to Use Internet Banking Services (Study in the BCA E-Banking Virtual Community)
- THE INFLUENCE OF CONVENIENCE, EASE OF USE AND SECURITY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (Study on Mandiri Internet Banking at Mandiri Bank Surabaya Commercial Branch)
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED EASE OF USE, PERCEIVED USEFULNESS, AND ATTITUDE TOWARD BEHAVIOR ON THE INTENTION TO USE OF INTERNET BANKING (Case Study at BNI 46 Bank Kln Brawijaya University Malang)
- Integration of SMS and Internet Protocols in Mobile Banking
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING, SERVICE QUALITY, PRODUCT REPUTATION, LOCATION, ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY WITH CUSTOMER SATISFACTION INTERMEDIATION
- The Internet Banking Service Quality at PT Bank XYZ Towards Customer Loyalty using E-Service Quality Method (E-SERVQUAL)
- The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Web Security, and Online Banking Information on Individual Interest in Using Internet Banking
- The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Convenience, Trust, Perceived Comfort, and Perceived Suitability on Internet Banking User Attitudes
- DETERMINANTS OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY USING THE WEBQUAL VERSION 4.0 METHOD AND ITS INFLUENCE ON

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF TOP BRAND E-CHANNEL BANK IN INDONESIA

- BUILDING CUSTOMER TRUST IN INTERNET BANKING
- ANALYSIS OF THE QUALITY OF BANK BUKOPIN'S INTERNET BANKING SERVICES USING THE FUZZY E-SERVQUAL METHOD, IPA, AND PROPOSED IMPROVEMENTS USING THE QFD METHOD
- LEGAL PROTECTION IN PROVIDING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES FOR CUSTOMER'S PERSONAL DATA AT BANK RURAL INDONESIA KLUNGKUNG BRANCH
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERSONALIZATION, COMPUTER SELF EFFICACY, AND TRUST ON PERCEIVED USEFULNESS IN INTERNET BANKING USERS AT PT. BANK BRI (Persero), Tbk. MADIUN BRANCH
- FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER INTEREST IN INTERNET BANKING
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF BANK CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS ON INTERNET BANKING ADOPTION (Study of Banking Customers Using Internet Banking in Surakarta City)
- TAM Analysis of Factors that Influence Customers Using BCA Internet Banking Services
- The influence of security, word of mouth, experience and information to brand trust on internet banking websites
- THE INFLUENCE OF COMFORT, TRUST, AND COMPLETENESS OF FEATURES ON DECISIONS TO USE INTERNET BANKING (Study of BCA Bank Customers in Purworejo Regency)
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK CUSTOMERS USING INTERNET BANKING FROM CYBERCRIME THREATS
- FACTORS INFLUENCING CUSTOMER INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING USING THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL FRAMEWORK IN SHARIA BANK
- MACROECONOMIC AND BANK SPECIFIC FACTORS DETERMINANTS OF BANK PROFITABILITY IN INDONESIA WITH THE IMPLEMENTATION OF INTERNET BANKING
- ANALYSIS OF KEY FACTORS FOR USE OF INTERNET BANKING (Case Study at PT. BNI (Persero) Tbk. Manado Branch Office)
- THE INFLUENCE OF EASE OF USE, CONVENIENCE ACCESSIBILITY, SAFETY OF USE AND CUSTOMER TRUST AS INTERVENING VARIABLES ON INTEREST IN RE-TRANSACTIONING E-BANKING (Case Study of Customers Using Internet Banking in Semarang City)
- The Impact of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Subjective Norm, and Experience Toward Student's Intention to Use Internet Banking
- The Effect of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction by Using Internet Banking Service in Jambi
- THE EFFECT OF IMPLEMENTING INTERNET BANKING ON STOCK RETURNS OF BANKING COMPANIES LISTED ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE
- THE INFLUENCE OF THE QUALITY OF BANKING SERVICES USING INTERNET BANKING ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY
- Segmentation of Internet Banking Services

- THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS ON RISKS, TRUST, BENEFITS, AND EASE OF USE ON INTERNET BANKING USE (Empirical Study of Commercial Bank Customers in Banda Aceh City)
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING ON THE LEVEL OF CUSTOMER TRUST IN BANK BRI SYARIAH KCP ARJAWINANGUN
- SERVICE QUALITY AND INTERNET BANKING GOVERNANCE FROM CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS
- THE ROLE OF ATTITUDE IN MEDIATING THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED USEFULNESS ON INTENTION TO USE INTERNET BANKING IN DENPASAR CITY
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK CUSTOMERS IN INTERNET BANKING BREAKING THROUGH MALWARE METHODS
- Determining factors influencing the use of internet banking services
- Application of the TAM Model to Internet Banking Service Users at the Situbondo Branch of Bank Jatim
- Analysis of the factors influencing the intention of accounting students in STIE Perbanas Surabaya to use Mandiri Internet Banking
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF MULTI DIMENSIONAL TRUST AND PERCEIVED RISK WITH THE UTAUT-LUO MODIFICATION MODEL ON THE USE OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES IN INDONESIA
- Factors that Influence the Level of Customer Trust in Internet Banking Users at Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI) Pekanbaru
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF BENEFITS, EASE OF USE, AND TRUST ON ATTITUDE TO USING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES (Comparative Study of Customers Using Internet Banking at Bank Mandiri Semarang Based on Income Level)
- THE INFLUENCE OF BRAND EQUITY AND INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY AT PT BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (PERSERO) TBK JENEPONTO BRANCH
- MICRO SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (UMKM) INTEREST IN USE OF INTERNET BANKING: A MODIFIED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) APPROACH
- THE INFLUENCE OF E-SERVICE QUALITY OF INTERNET BANKING USERS ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (Study of Bank Central Asia Customers in Malang City)
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED USEFULNESS AND PERCEIVED EASE OF USE ON INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING WITH ATTITUDE TOWARD USING AS AN INTERVENING VARIABLE
- The Effect of Usefulness, Ease of Use, Risk, and Trust to Behavioral Intention in the Use of Internet Banking
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS AFFECTING CUSTOMER INTEREST IN TRANSACTING VIA INTERNET BANKING AT PT. BRI. SINGARAJA BRANCH
- GENERATION Y AND ADOPTION OF INTERNET BANKING AMONG CUSTOMERS IN INDONESIA USING THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) FRAMEWORK
- FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CUSTOMERS TO CONTINUE USING INTERNET BANKING FACILITIES AT ASIA CENTRAL BANK
- Determinants of the Internet Islamic Banking Services Adoption in Jordan

- ANALYSIS OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICE QUALITY USING THE E-SERVQUAL METHOD AT BANK XYZ
- SIX STRENGTHS OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES: A REVIEW OF CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS
- THE INFLUENCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY CAPABILITY, CONVENIENCE, RISKS AND SERVICE FEATURES ON CUSTOMER INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING (Empirical Study of Bank Rakyat Indonesia Customers in Banjarmasin City)
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION (CASE STUDY ON CUSTOMERS OF THE INDONESIAN SYARIAH BANK PALEMBANG BRANCH)
- The Influence of E-Marketing and E-CRM on Customer Loyalty Using Bank Syariah Mandiri Internet Banking
- Customer participation in the creation and implementation of the service for internet banking
- Internet Banking Service Features at Banks in Indonesia
- ANALYSIS OF INTERNET BANKING ACCEPTANCE FACTORS USING THE TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) APPROACH WITH THE ADDITION OF THE ROLE OF EXTRINSIC AND INTRINSIC MOTIVATION
- PROCESS OF IMPLEMENTING RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS IN INTERNET BANKING AGREEMENTS AND GUARANTEES PROVIDED BY BANK TO CUSTOMERS USING INTERNET BANKING (STUDY AT BNI BANK PADANG BRANCH)
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEIVED RISK, SOCIAL NORMS, USEFULNESS, AND TRUST ON THE ADOPTION OF MOBILE BANKING AND INTERNET BANKING
- The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Ease of Use, Risk on Customer Attitudes and Behavioral Intentions in Using Internet Banking at PT. Bank Muamalat Indonesia, Tbk Jember Branch
- Analysis of Factors that Influence the Use of Internet Banking in Jabodetabek
- A Study of The Factors That Influence The Level of Consumer Satisfaction Towards The Use of Internet Banking
- THE BANK'S RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS CUSTOMERS FOR INTERNET BANKING SERVICES (Study at Bank BRI Syariah Medan Branch)
- THE BEHAVIOR IN UTILIZING INTERNET BANKING AS COMMUNICATION MEDIA
- Assessment of Internet Banking Services Continued Use: Role of Socio-Cognitive and Relational View
- Behavioral Intention Analysis on Internet Banking Usage at Bank XYZ Bogor
- APPLICATION OF K-MEANS AND K-MEDOIDS CLUSTERING ON INTERNET BANKING DATA AT BANK XYZ
- Factors that influence customer interest in using internet banking services using UTAUT (Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology) (Study of BRI Internet Banking Users)
- THE INFLUENCE OF PERCEPTIONS OF EASE, USEFULNESS, RISK AND TRUST ON CUSTOMER INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING AT PT BANK BUKOPIN Tbk BANJARMASIN

- THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL ON BEHAVIORAL INTENTION OF INTERNET BANKING USERS IN MANADO
- CORRELATION OF EFFICIENCY LEVELS, SECURITY WITH INTERNET BANKING AS AN ALTERNATIVE TO BRANCHLESS BANKING PT BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK IN SURABAYA
- The Influence of Internet Banking on Customer Interest in Transactions Using the Technology Acceptance Model
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK CUSTOMERS DUE TO ACCOUNT BREAKING THROUGH INTERNET BANKING
- USE OF THE BANKNESIA APPLICATION IN FINANCIAL MUTATION REPORTING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES
- Influence of Interest in Using PT Internet Banking Services. Haldin Pacific Semesta in Business Transactions
- The Influence of Internet Banking Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction at PT Bank Negara Indonesia Persero Tbk KC Madiun
- BANKING TRANSACTIONS VIA INTERNET BANKING IN INDONESIA BASED ON LAW NUMBER 19 OF 2016 CONCERNING INFORMATION AND ELECTRONIC TRANSACTIONS
- The Use Analysis of Internet Banking among SMEs Entrepreneurs
- The Effect of Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Risk on the Utilization of Internet Banking (Study on BRI Internet Banking Customers in Semarang City)
- Factors that Influence Customer Satisfaction Using Internet Banking at Bank Muamalat
- Motivations for Using Internet Banking Services and Their Relationship with Gender Differences
- Modern Trends of Internet Banking Market in Supply Chain of Russia
- Factors affecting the internet financial reporting (IFR) in banking sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX)
- EVALUATION OF THE INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK INTERNET BANKING SERVICES ON USABILITY ASPECTS
- INTERNAL AUDIT: THE APPLICATION OF RISK MANAGEMENT AND ELECTRONIC CHANNELS INTERNET BANKING THROUGH THE AUDIT MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE QUALITY OF FINTECH GOVERNANCE IN BANKING INDUSTRY
- FACTORS AFFECTING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING
- Factors that influence the decision to use internet banking for BRI bank customers in Surabaya
- Effectiveness of the PermataNet Internet Banking Information System Case study of PT Bank Permata Tbk using AMOS
- THE INFLUENCE OF ADVERTISING, EASE OF USE, RISKS AND COMPANY IMAGE ON THE INTEREST OF BRI INTERNET BANKING CUSTOMERS ON BRI CUSTOMERS IN THE MALABAR TANGERANG UNIT
- ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON INTERNET BANKING: A CASE STUDY ON BANK SAHABAT SAMPOERNA
- INTERNET BANKING (IBANK) SYSTEM DESIGN USING ONE-TIME-PASSWORD (OTP) FOR SECURING TRANSACTIONS (CASE STUDY OF BANK MEGA, Tbk)

- LEGAL PROTECTION OF CUSTOMERS IN TRANSACTIONS VIA INTERNET BANKING (Study at PT Bank Pembangunan Daerah Jawa Timur Tbk.)
- The Influence of Online Service Quality on Internet Banking Customer Satisfaction, Commitment and Loyalty in Denpasar City
- FACTORS INFLUENCING INTEREST IN USE OF INTERNET BANKING AT BANK BCA SURABAYA
- ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON THE QUALITY OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES AT PT BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (Persero) Tbk. BANYUMANIK SEMARANG UNIT
- USE OF TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) IN ANALYZING THE BEHAVIORAL INTENTION OF INTERNET BANKING USAGE IN TELKOM UNIVERSITY STUDENTS
- FACTOR ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING ACCEPTANCE ON BANK CUSTOMERS IN SURABAYA
- ASPECTS OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF CUSTOMER'S PERSONAL DATA IN PROVIDING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES (Case Study at PT. Bank Mandiri Baturaja Branch)
- Development of a Web-Based Savings and Loans Cooperative Internet Banking Application
- Analysis of the Influence of Banking Information Security Systems on Internet Banking User Customers
- THE BANK'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR CUSTOMER SECURITY IN TRANSACTING VIA INTERNET BANKING BANK JATENG
- THE INFLUENCE OF RISKS, BENEFITS AND EASE OF USE ON CUSTOMERS' CONFIDENCE IN USING INTERNET BANKING IN PEKANBARU
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR USERS OF INTERNET BANKING CUSTOMERS FOLLOWING CHANGES IN INFORMATION AND ELECTRONIC TRANSACTIONS LAW
- Alpha and Beta Testing on PT Bank Mega, Tbk's Internet Banking (Ibank) System Development
- THE USE OF INTERNET BANKING AND AUTOMATIC TELLER MACHINE RELATED TO INCREASING BUSINESS BY MSME PLAYERS IN WONOMULYO'S MAIN MARKET
- THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER KNOWLEDGE AND SERVICE QUALITY ON INDIVIDUAL INTERESTS OF BANJARMASIN INTERNET BANKING USERS
- ANALYSIS OF PERCEPTIONS OF BENEFITS AND EASE OF USE ON INTERNET BANKING INTEREST AND ADOPTION AT PT. BANK PEOPLE INDONESIA (PERSERO) Tbk, PANGKALAN KERINCI BRANCH
- BANKING TRANSACTIONS VIA INTERNET BANKING
- FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CUSTOMER DECISIONS TO USE PT INTERNET BANKING SERVICES. BANK MESTIKA RANTAUPRAPAT
- LIABILITY IN TRANSACTIONS VIA INTERNET BANKING
- IMPACT OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES IN INCREASING CUSTOMER SATISFACTION
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CUSTOMERS USING INTERNET BANKING
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF INTERNET BANKING CUSTOMER DATA IN BRI CITY BUKITTINGGI AND PAYAKUMBUH

- Analysis of Acceptance of Use Internet Banking and Mobile Banking, Case Study: Standard Application in XYZ Company
- ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF THE UTAUT MODEL ON INTERNET BANKING BEHAVIORAL INTEREST AND USE
- The Influence of Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Convenience, and Trust on Interest in Using Internet Banking
- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE IN CONVENTIONAL COMMERCIAL BANKS LISTED ON THE INDONESIAN STOCK EXCHANGE (PERIOD 2015 - 2018)
- FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE CUSTOMERS TO ADOPTING INTERNET BANKING TECHNOLOGY IN WEST KALIMANTAN
- ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION FROM INTERNET BANKING USERS (CASE STUDY IN THE SURABAYA BUSINESS AREA)
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INFLUENCING INTENTION TO USE INTERNET BANKING BASED ON TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE MODEL (TAM) (Empirical Study of BCA Bank Customers in Malang City)
- ANALYSIS OF CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON THE QUALITY OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES AT PT BANK DEARAH JAVA CENTRAL JAVA PATI BRANCH OFFICE
- APPLICATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF ABSOLUTE LIABILITY IN RELATION TO CONSUMER LOSSES FROM THE USE OF INTERNET BANKING PRODUCTS
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE RIGHTS OF BANK CUSTOMERS AS CONSUMERS OF INTERNET BANKING SERVICES FROM CYBERCRIME THREATS
- FACTORS INFLUENCING STUDENTS' INTEREST IN USING INTERNET BANKING (STUDY ON SYIAH KUALA UNIVERSITY STUDENTS)
- LEGAL ARRANGEMENTS REGARDING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES IN BANKING TRANSACTIONS
- BEHAVIORAL USAGE OF INTERNET BANKING AS A FINANCIAL TRANSACTION TOOL: BEHAVIORAL USAGE OF INTERNET BANKING AS FINANCIAL TRANSACTION TOOL
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- The Influence of Internet Banking on Customer Satisfaction at PT. Bank Bri Syariah Kebayoran Baru
- THE INFLUENCE OF USEFUL, EASE, TRUST, AND CONVENIENCE INTEREST IN CUSTOMER BEHAVIOR AND DECISION USING INTERNET BANKING IN THE UNIT OF PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK TBK. BRANCH AHMAD YANI MAKASSAR
- Analysis of Student Interest in Using BNI Syariah Bank Internet Banking Services
- THE INFLUENCE OF RELATIONSHIP MARKETING, INTERNET BANKING PRODUCT QUALITY AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION ON CUSTOMER LOYALTY IN BANK BRI UNIT MEDAN SUNGGAL
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- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF BANKING TRANSACTIONS VIA INTERNET BANKING IN MANADO
- Internet Banking Service Quality: Building Satisfaction and Customer Trust

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- ASPECTS OF LEGAL PROTECTION OF CUSTOMERS' PERSONAL DATA IN PROVIDING INTERNET BANKING SERVICES (Case Study at Bank Bukopin Kediri Branch)
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- Determination of Internet Banking Customer Satisfaction - Study at SOE Bank in Indonesia
- The Impact Of E-Service Quality To Wards Customer Satisfaction On The User Of Internet Banking In PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia Tbk (Persero)
- The Influence of Internet Banking Use and Customer Data Protection on Cybercrime in Denpasar City
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- Perception of Benefits, Ease of Use and Interest in Using Internet Banking with Attitude as an Intervening Variable
- Conceptual Model on Internet Banking Acceptance in China with Social Network Influence
- ANALYSIS OF THE INFLUENCE OF CUSTOMER PERCEPTIONS ON INTERNET BANKING USE
- Juridical Review of the Protection of Banking Customers Using Internet Banking Services
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- THE INFLUENCE OF INTERNET BANKING, MOBILE BANKING AND ATM ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION OF BSI KC PALEMBANG SIMPANG PATAL
- USE OF MOBILE BANKING AND INTERNET BANKING DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC AT PT BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI TANGERANG BSD BRANCH OFFICE
- Strategy to Increase Customer Interest in Using Internet Mobile Banking (Case Study at Bank Syariah Mandiri in Lhokseumawe)
- COLLECTION/PAYMENT OF TREASURER TRANSACTION TAX FOR "X" OFFICE EXPENSES USING INTERNET BANKING: -
- DETERMINANTS OF CUSTOMERS' ADAPTATION TO INTERNET BANKING: EVIDENCE FROM GREATER JAKARTA AREA, INDONESIA
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- The Influence of Psychological Factors on Decisions to Use BCA Internet Banking in Palembang City
- THE INFLUENCE OF GOOD CORPORATE GOVERNANCE ON INTERNET FINANCIAL REPORTING (Study on Financial Sector Banking Sub-Sector Listed in the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2013 to 2020)

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 271 research topic mappings using literature studies around previous research journals, the researcher found 271 Research topics regarding *Internet Banking* in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

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